

World Safety Journal

A peer-reviewed journal,
published by the World Safety Organization

Journal Homepage:
<https://worldsafety.org/wso-world-safety-journal/>

Adapting AI and ChatBots in Safety Applications and Education

David Gilkey^{1,*}, Lorri Birkenbuel¹, and Michael Kennedy¹

¹ Montana Technological University, Department of Safety, Health and Industrial Hygiene,
1300 West park St. Butte, MT 59701

KEYWORDS

Artificial Intelligence;
AI;
AI Assistance;
Safety;
Safety Education;
Student Impressions;
Student Opinion.

ABSTRACT

AI will revolutionize industries beyond expectations. Popularity and use have risen more than 60% from 2023 to 2024. Adoption of AI in many business sectors is planned, underway, or already implemented. Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) has adopted AI to enhance capacities and improve worker safety, health, and wellbeing. This project investigated 25 university student's impressions and opinions of AI use on assignments in two OSH courses. They reported very positive impressions and opinions, overwhelmingly supportive for: 1) Development of New Skills and Use New Skills to Solve problems or Think About Solutions Using Concepts or Methods Taught in the Course Because of ChatGPT and/or OpenAI, p -value < 0.001 , and 2) Develop Mastery and Competencies in OSH/IH for Professional Practice, p -value $= 0.062 > 0.001$, and 3) Overall Assessment of ChatGPT and/or Open AI, p -value < 0.001 . The OSH sector is using AI for monitoring, data collection and analysis, estimates of severity as well as appropriate interventions and controls. The use of environmental and wearable technologies enables AI to collect real-time data and warn workers of hazards and risks. The use of AI is not without concerns for privacy of personal information, unnecessary surveillance, and job displacement. Despite concerns, the expanding use of AI must include OSH to keep up with new and innovative approaches to a safe and healthy workplace and improved worker wellbeing.

1. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

The concept of artificial intelligence (AI) entered the scientific literature significantly in the 1950s (Ge & Hu, 2020; Russel & Novig, 2010). AI technologies have progressively made their way into many areas of human activity including robotics, transport, aerospace, banking and finance, biotechnology, emergency services, medicine, law, manufacturing, media, music, the military, operations management, personnel management, and retail packaging (Schorr & Rappaport, 1989). Approximately 20% of all businesses have already integrated AI and another 55% are planning to do so in the near future (Pluralsight, 2024). The AI market is expected to reach \$15.7 trillion by 2030 (Dreamhunter, 2024). Much of this growth is in artificial intelligence (AI). AI that generates new content from what it is trained,

* *Corresponding Author*: dgilkey@mtech.edu

using large language models (LLMs) for deep learning to understand, predict and generate natural human-like language (Brynjolfsson, Li & Raymond, 2023; Shen et al. 2023). ChatGPT/OpenAI is a LLM recently reported to reach over 100 million users (Walsh, 2024). Due to their neural network architecture, LLMs can be highly accurate and creative (Shen et al. 2023), hence, their popularity.

The United States (US) is ranked number one in government readiness when it comes to AI for public services (Dempere et al., 2023). Researchers have anticipated that AI will replace up to seven percent of all jobs while aiding 63% of all positions (Dempere et al., 2023). ChatGPT/OpenAI has been found to be very effective in customer support with reduced time to solution and increased productivity (Nazir & Wang, 2023). ChatGPT is a LLM which learns from an extremely large neural network of text data and has machine learning capability. While AI may serve very effectively as a personal assistant managing schedules, setting reminders, reading news, controlling phone devices, and sending messages it has many other applications, strengths as well as weaknesses. ChatGPT and other LLMs can provide additional functions such as interpretation and summary of articles, news updates, and reports, thus reducing the time once required to read and understand the entire document (Nazir & Wang, 2023). Chatbots like ChatGPT can also create text for articles, news updates, and reports on nearly any subject with ease as well as send emails or make social media posts in multiple languages (Nazir & Wang, 2023).

2. AI IN OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY AND HEALTH

AI is rapidly being applied to safety and security (Cebulla et al., 2023). This new technology has enhanced worksite and worker surveillance using dashboards to improve communication, monitoring of activities onsite, safe work practices as well as productivity. Cybersecurity has seen a major application of AI to protect proprietary, financial, and personal information (Cubella et al., 2023). Risk Evolution, Detection, Evaluation, and Control of Accidents (REDECA) is a framework for exposure assessment and risk reduction utilizing AI technologies such as remote and wearable sensors for data collection and analysis (Pishgar et al., 2021). Authors have highlighted the role that AI plays in estimating the occurrence of accidents, the need for warnings, and corrective actions and AI are evaluated for its applications in oil and gas, mining, transportation, construction, and agriculture to identify its role in injury prevention (Pishgar et al., 2021).

The oil and gas sector is embracing AI around the world. AI offers a paradigm shift in the way risk mitigation is handled (Arinze et al., 2024). AI applications are able to enhance exploration, production, transportation, and refining processes. Its capacities can optimize resource allocation, streamline operations, and maximize outputs (Arinze et al., 2024). Within the oil and gas industry, AI can evaluate large amounts of loss data, exposure assessment data, remote monitoring of real-time data to detect anomalies and predict safety hazards allowing proactive interventions and effective prevention of incidence (Arinze et al., 2024).

In the transportation domain, AI is revolutionizing the sector with its autonomous capabilities (Perez-Cerrolaza et al., 2024). AI will enable the development of the next generation of autonomous vehicles. Using machine learning tools, safety systems are optimized with AI drive algorithms. Working with transportation engineers AI can develop safety critical systems to ensure safer workplaces and processes, see figure 1. Safety critical systems require precise and accurate decisions to avoid catastrophic outcomes. AI is a major factor in the expansion of unmanned aerial and autonomous vehicles. Success in advances have led to use of autonomous vehicles in avionics, railway, automotive, industrial trucks, and robotics (Perez-Cerrolaza et al., 2024). The rapid expansion in development and use has led to corollary safety standards such as the ISO 21448 standard, Safety Of The Intended Functionality (SOTIF)

that focuses on ensuring the safety of advanced driver assistance systems and automated driving systems by addressing potential hazards. The standard complements the existing functional safety standard, ISO 26262, which primarily focuses on hardware and software failures (SGS, 2024). Ethical implications have had considerable discussion and action. Standards are the manifestation of values and ethics in societies leading to varied approaches for ensuring safety inclusion of AI applications. Australia was one of the first countries to pass a list of ethical principles that pertain to AI (Department of Industry, Science and Resources, 2019).

Figure 1

Safety-Critical System in Industrial Transportation Old vs AI Model

Note: From Perez-Cerrolaza, J., Abella, J., Borg, M., Donzella, C., Cerquides, J., Cazorla, F. J., ... & Flores, J. L. (2024, p 176:9.). Artificial intelligence for safety-critical systems in industrial and transportation domains: A survey. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 56(7), 1-40.

Australian researchers have developed a scorecard for evaluating safety based on ethical principles published in recent years (Cebulla et al., 2024). The AI Work Health and Safety (WHS) Scorecard is an ethical framework or tool for industries of all types to evaluate and manage risks associated with hazardous exposures to workers, see figure 2. Companies can use this tool to evaluate their success in including equity, contribution, openness, and responsibility in using AI in the workplace. Using the scorecard also provides an opportunity to identify gaps in human-AI relations and missing measures that can be improved. Ethical principles should enhance the workplace climate and support safety and the dignity of workers. Figure 2 identifies hazards, characteristics, ethical principles and AI canvas of enhancements.

As the researchers explored their matrix, insight was gained through AI experts consulting the frontline AI users (Cebulla et al., 2024). The team believes AI will change economies throughout the world. The focus appears to be on societal levels, economic success through increased efficiencies and production. Many fear that WHS may not be a priority so they are working hard to ensure OSH standards and laws are in place and followed (Cebulla et al., 2024).

Figure 2

Conceptual Integration of AI Canvas, AI Ethics Principles and Safe Work Characteristics

Note: From Cebulla, A., Szpak, Z., Howell, C., Knight, G., & Hussain, S. (2023). Applying ethics to AI in the workplace: the design of a scorecard for Australian workplace health and safety. AI & society, 38(2), 919-935.

John Howard, Director of NIOSH, spoke directly to this concern (CDC, 2019). He held a webinar titled, “Artificial Intelligence: Implications for the Future of Work”. The one-hour webinar detailed the promise of AI in business systems through multiple tools such as using sensors, robotics, data analytics, and decision support systems and more. Dr. Howard recommended that stakeholders must be aware of the implications that AI brings to the work system. He recommends that prior to introduction and adoption of AI-supported enhancements make an explicit and through review of their benefits and risks, be certain that safety and health is fully integrated include those new hazards associated with AI (CDC, 2019). Research suggests expanding opportunities to use AI exist within the field of occupational safety and health (Pishgar et al., 2021). Big data, robotics, remote sensing, and wearable technologies are just the beginning. Many are now recommending students have skills for using AI as they enter the job market. We found no studies investigating student perceptions and opinions associated with the use of AI. This investigation was intended to identify and evaluate student perceptions regarding use of ChatGPT/OpenAI on assignments.

3. METHODOLOGY

This cross-sectional study was designed to investigate student impressions and opinions associated with AI use in the classroom. A 50-question survey on the use of ChatGPT/OpenAI in their assessment tasks was developed. Questions were in the form of statements, respondents were asked for their level of agreement using a Likert scale 1 to 5 was used to assess the level of student's agreement with statements, where 1 = highly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neither agree or disagree, 4 = agree, and 5 = highly agreed. Questions were grouped in content areas: 1) Development of New Skills and Use New Skills to Solve problems or Think About Solutions Using Concepts or Methods Taught in the Course Because of ChatGPT and/or Open AI, 2) Develop Mastery and Competencies in OSH/IH for Professional Practice, and 3) Overall Assessment of ChatGPT and/or Open AI. Anonymous surveys were sent to 50 students enrolled in the course at the end of the semester. Students were asked if ChatGPT enabled them to develop new skills, to solve problems or think about solutions using concepts or methods taught in their course, if ChatGPT helped develop mastery and competencies in safety science professional practice, and what was their overall assessment of ChatGPT as a learning tool. This project was carried out in two university level OSH courses ergonomics and epidemiology. Data were analysed using Chi-Square test for equal proportions in MiniTab™, version 21. Basic descriptives and frequencies were derived.

4. RESULTS

Twenty-five completed surveys were returned for a response rate of 50%. Results were overwhelmingly supportive and significant, p-value < 0.001.

Table 1 presents the student perception and opinion of AI and its ability to aid students in news skills and problem solving. Of those students surveyed, 84% either strongly agreed or agreed that ChatGPT/OpenAI enabled them to solve problems differently and informed a new prospective, p-value < 0.001. Ninety-two percent (92%) highly agreed or agreed that ChatGPT/OpenAI enabled them to learn new information, p-value < 0.001. Seventy percent (70%) highly agreed or agreed that ChatGPT/OpenAI were practical tools for solving OSH/IH problems, p-value < 0.001. Eighty-four percent (84%) highly agreed or agreed that they would continue to use ChatGPT/Open AI to solve problems into the future, p-value < 0.001.

Table 2 presents respondent level of agreement with statements associated with mastery and competency in OSH and IH topics. Eighty Percent (80%) highly agreed or agreed that ChatGPT/OpenAI helped them better apply practice methods with confidence and apply new OSH/IH skills to solve real-world problems, p-value < 0.001. Seventy-six percent (86%) highly agreed or agreed that ChatGPT/OpenAI helped them apply basic skills taught in the course and in their application to grad school, p-value < 0.001. Table 3 presents respondent opinions and perceptions about the overall utility and impact of ChatGPT/OpenAI. Seventy-six percent (76%) highly agreed or agreed that ChatGPT/OpenAI was great and everything that they were expecting, p-value < 0.001.

Sixty-eight percent (68%) highly agreed or agreed that ChatGPT/Open AI was more than they were expecting p-value < 0.001. And finally, 88% highly agreed or agreed that they would continue to use ChatGPT/Open AI, p-value < 0.001.

Table 1*Distribution of Responses by Number and Percent for New Skills and Problem Solving*

Questions	Highly Agree (n)%	Agree %	Neither Agree Nor Disagree %	Disagree %	Strongly Disagree %	P-Value
I was able to see and act to solve problems differently with a new perspective.	(14)56	(7)28	(4)16	0	0	<0.001
I was able to learn new information using ChatGPT/AI.	(18)72	(5)20	(2)8	0	0	<0.001
I was able to see and act to solve problems differently with new skills and tools.	(16)64	(6)24	(3)12	0	0	<0.001
I began to apply new skills to solve problems after using ChatGPT/AI.	(13)52	(9)36	(3)12	0	0	<0.001
I believe that ChatGPT/AI are practical tools for Solving OSH/IJ problems.	(14)56	(6)24	(5)20	0	0	<0.001
I began to realize that other disciplines and specialties are relevant to OSH/IH practice.	(14)56	(7)28	(4)16	0	0	<0.001
I will recommend ChatGPT to others to find solutions to OSH/IH problems.	(17)68	(2)8	(4)16	(2)8	0	<0.001
I will continue to use ChatGPT or Open AI to solve problems in the future.	(18)72	(3)12	(2)8	(2)8	0	<0.001

Table 2*Distribution of Responses by Number and Percent for Mastery and Competency*

Questions	Highly Agree (n)%	Agree %	Neither Agree Nor Disagree %	Disagree %	Strongly Disagree %	P-Value
ChatGPT helped me better apply practice methods with confidence	(15)60	(5)20	(3)12	(1)4	(1)4	<0.001
ChatGPT helped me apply new OHS/IH skills to solve real-world problems	(12)48	(8)32	(3)12	(2)8	0	0.005
ChatGPT/AI helped me see that I can collaborate with others to solve OHS/IH problems	(10)40	(8)32	(5)20	(1)4	(1)4	0.014
ChatGPT helped me teach OHS/IH principles and methods to others	(10)40	(4)16	(7)28	(1)4	(3)12	0.014
ChatGPT helped me apply for entry-level OHS/IH positions	(7)28	(4)16	(6)24	0	(7)28	0.062
ChatGPT helped me apply the basic skills taught in the course and I will be applying for graduate school in IH/OHS/Ergo	(12)48	(7)28	(1)4	0	(5)20	<0.001

Table 3*Distribution of Responses by Number and Percent for Overall Assessment of ChatGPT/Open AI*

Questions	Highly Agree (n)%	Agree %	Neither Agree Nor Disagree %	Disagree %	Strongly Disagree %	P- Value
ChatGPT/Ai was great, everything I was expecting	(16)64	(3)12	(5)20	(1)4	0	<0.001
ChatGPT/AI was more than I was expecting	(13)52	(4)16	(8)32	0	0	<0.001
I will continue to use ChatGPT or Open AI	(17)68	(5)20	(1)4	(1)4	(1)4	<0.001

5. DISCUSSION, CONCERNS, AND LIMITATIONS

This investigation evaluated student feedback on their perceptions and opinions of AI when completing assignments in two OSH topic areas: Ergonomics and Epidemiology. The overwhelming responses were positive, indicating that students felt the tool was useful and effective in achieving learning goals, skills development and mastery in OSH. There is a paucity of publications that focus on student opinions and impressions of AI. Most of the literature is focused on how AI is used to provide feedback to students regarding their productivity and performance on assignments (Atherton, Topham and Khan, 2024; Fauzi et al., 2023; Hooda et al., 2024; Nawaz et al., 2022; Nazaretsky et al., 2024). AI was used to evaluate student course feedback but, without inquiry about how AI impacted student learning experience in the classroom (Nawaz et al., 2022). AI is frequently being used to provide personalized feedback to students for enhanced learning and for analysis of student performance to develop new approaches to teaching and learning interventions (Atherton, Topham and Khan, 2024; Hooda et al., 2024; Nawaz et al., 2022; Nazaretsky et al., 2024).

There are several concerns associated with the AI juggernaut. AI can hallucinate and give wrong answers. Learning to feed correct information in can minimize misinformation (Snowflake, 2024). Church (2024) found as much as 30% error rate on student assignments. He strongly recommends proofing AI output. Another major concern for AI users is the risk of security information breaches (Pluralsight, 2024). Organizations and personal users are concerned about their privacy and disclosure of personal and proprietary information (Resnick, 2024). Business owners need to be aware of the risk of deep fakes penetrating their system and gaining access to proprietary and confidential information. Deep fakes are digital entities that can cause harm and spread misinformation. AI can further facilitate the development of sophisticated malicious malware to cause further havoc for organizations (Pluralsight, 2024). Organizations are also concerned over-reliance on technology and lack of technical skills to use AI for their purposes (Dreamhunter, 2024). While AI has great promise for customer service, others worry about the negative impacts with some customers. Investigators have identified concerns over constraints in self directed learning with AI because curriculums dictate goals and not the user. In a similar fashion AI is built on close-ended tasks and not open-ended problem-solving (Resnick, 2024). In a recent survey of CEOs, 42% expressed a concern for general humanity overall in the next five to 10 years (Dreamhunter, 2024). An open letter has been drafted to call of a suspension of AI training and adoption until more is understood with > 33,000 signatures including Elon Musk. The promises of AI are numerous as are the risks, threats and concerns (Dreamhunter, 2024; Resnick, 2024).

Despite concerns, AI has been adapted to several areas within OSH including disease and injury prevention through occupational health risk assessment (Liu et al, 2023), drones and unmanned aerial vehicles (Perez-Cerrolaza, 2024), wearable technologies (Nahavandi et al., 2022) remote sensors (Kirshnamoorthy, 2024), big data analysis with estimates of injury, illness severity and interventions (Kakhi, Freeman & Mosher, 2019; Niehaus et al, 2022), monitoring of noise exposures, hazard assessment, job descriptions, exoskeletons, training and education, selection of smart PPE, drones, worker surveillance, and emergency management activation (Shah & Mishra, 2024). Enhancing worker safety can be accomplished using AI with wearable sensors that can track vital signs, location, and communication with centralized control systems (Krishnamoorthy et al., 2024). The applications in safety continue to expand. An eight-country survey found that 80% of workers reported AI improved their performance (Lane, Williams & Broecke, 2023). Workers in that same study also reported that AI had improved their working conditions. Employers reported that AI will also require new skills for workers and will likely lead to some personnel reduction (Lane, Williams & Broecke, 2023).

We recognize that our study has limitations, the sample size is small and does not represent the larger student population. We also recognize the possibility of response bias and that students may have potentially scored statements higher on the Likert scales to please the professor.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

AI is here to stay and rapidly being adapted to a wide variety of business operations. Its use was expected to grow 37.5% annually from 2023-2030 (Hann & Watts, 2024) but in fact has risen 61% since 2023 (Dreamhunter, 2024). There is a consensus that professors should talk about AI tools with their students (Supiano, 2023). The OSH community has concerns that safety and health may be overlooked in the pursuit of profits (CDC, 2019). Applications have also been adopted in public safety (Adefemi et al., 2023). Many approaches to using AI have been successful including environmental and personal monitoring of safety and health hazards. The use of AI in the evaluation of big data provides the opportunity for predicting and proactively maintaining safe and healthy workplaces (Kakhki, Freeman and Mosher, 2019). While there are many positive and expanding applications for safety enhancements, others are greatly concerned about the rapidly spreading, uncontrolled expansion of AI applications and adaptations. Experts are optimistic and believe that AI will be used as an assistance tool to help OSH professionals in their work (Niehaus, Hartwig, Rosen & Wischniewski, 2022). Ethical considerations have been published and promoted however, virtually no legal constraints exist. It is predicted that AI skills will become essential in the very near future. As companies consider adoption of AI in operations, it is recommended to evaluate possible negative impacts and threats. Employ those AI application that support effective safety and health practices that remain ethical and support worker wellbeing (Shah & Mishra, 2024). This study supports the use of AI in the classroom to enhance learning. As AI continues to expand in all areas, it is essential that university curriculums include AI to build competency for use and integration in OSH practice to serve business operations.

REFERENCES

- Adefemi, A., Ukpoju, E., Adekoya, O. Abatan, A. and Adegbite, O. (2023). Artificial intelligence in environmental health and public safety: A comprehensive review of USA strategies. (n.d.). World Journal Of Advanced Research and Reviews. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.20.3.2591>
- Arinze, C. A., Izionworu, V. O., Isong, D., Daudu, C. D., & Adefemi, A. (2024). Integrating artificial intelligence into engineering processes for improved efficiency and safety in oil and gas operations. *Open Access Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 6(1), 39-51.

- Atherton, P., Topham, L., & Khan, W. (2024). AI and student feedback. *EDULEARN24 Proceedings*, 79-88.
- Brynjolfsson, E., Li, D., & Raymond, L. R. (2023). Generative AI at work (No. w31161). National Bureau of Economic Research.
- CDC. (2019). Artificial intelligence: Implications for the future of work. Accessed on October 27, 2024 <https://blogs.cdc.gov/niosh-science-blog/2019/08/26/ai/>.
- Cebulla, A., Szpak, Z., Howell, C., Knight, G., & Hussain, S. (2023). Applying ethics to AI in the workplace: the design of a scorecard for Australian workplace health and safety. *AI & society*, 38(2), 919-935.
- Church, K. (2024). Emerging trends: When can users trust GPT, and when should they intervene?. *Natural Language Engineering*, 1-11.
- Dept of Industry, Science and Resources. (2019). Australia's AI ethical principles. Australian government. Accessed on August 24, 2024. <https://www.industry.gov.au/publications/australias-artificial-intelligence-ethics-framework/australias-ai-ethics-principles>.
- Dempere, J., Modugu, K., Hesham, A., & Ramasamy, L. K. (2023, September). The impact of ChatGPT on higher education. In *Frontiers in Education* (Vol. 8, p. 1206936). <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2023.1206936>
- Dreamhunter, J. (2024). 100+ impressive AI statistics for 2024. Access September 20, 2024 <https://juliety.com/ai-statistics>.
- Fauzi, F., Tuhuteru, L., Sampe, F., Ausat, A. M. A., & Hatta, H. R. (2023). Analysing the role of ChatGPT in improving student productivity in higher education. *Journal on Education*, 5(4), 14886-14891.
- Ge, Z., & Hu, Y. (2020, April). Innovative application of artificial intelligence (ai) in the management of higher education and teaching. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1533, No. 3, p. 032089). IOP Publishing.
- Haan, K. & Watts, R. (2024, April). 24 top AI statistics and trends in 2024. *Forbes Advisor*. Accessed on April 23, 2024 [24 Top AI Statistics & Trends In 2024 – Forbes Advisor](#)
- Hooda, M., Rana, C., Dahiya, O., Rizwan, A., & Hossain, M. S. (2022). Artificial intelligence for assessment and feedback to enhance student success in higher education. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2022(1), 5215722.
- Kakhki, F. D., Freeman, S. A., & Mosher, G. A. (2019). Evaluating machine learning performance in predicting injury severity in agribusiness industries. *Safety science*, 117, 257-262.
- Kirshnamoorthy, G., Sistla, S., Venkatasubbu, S. and Periyasamy, V. (2024). Enhancing Worker Safety in Manufacturing with IoT and ML. (n.d.). *International Journal For Multidisciplinary Research*. <https://doi.org/10.36948/ijfmr.2024.v06i01.14203>
- Lane, M., Williams, M., Broecke, S. (2023). The impact of AI on the workplace: Main findings from the OECD AI surveys of employers and workers. Accessed on September 20, 2024. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/the-impact-of-ai-on-the-workplace-main-findings-from-the-oecd-ai-surveys-of-employers-and-workers_ea0a0fe1-en.html.
- Liu, R., Liu, H. C., Shi, H., & Gu, X. (2023). Occupational health and safety risk assessment: A systematic literature review of models, methods, and applications. *Safety science*, 160, 106050.
- Montenegro-Rueda, M., Fernández-Cerero, J., Fernández-Batanero, J, and López-Meneses, E. (2023). Impact of the Implementation of ChatGPT in Education: A Systematic Review. *Computers*, 12, 153. doi.org/10.3390/computers12080153
- Nahavandi, D., Alizadehsani, R., Khosravi, A., & Acharya, U. R. (2022). Application of artificial intelligence in wearable devices: Opportunities and challenges. *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, 213, 106541.

- Nawaz, R., Sun, Q., Shardlow, M., Kontonatsios, G., Aljohani, N. R., Visvizi, A., & Hassan, S. U. (2022). Leveraging AI and machine learning for national student survey: actionable insights from textual feedback to enhance quality of teaching and learning in UK's higher education. *Applied Sciences*, 12(1), 514.
- Nazaretsky, T., Mejia-Domenzain, P., Swamy, V., Frej, J., & Käser, T. (2024, September). AI or human? Evaluating student feedback perceptions in higher education. In *European Conference on Technology Enhanced Learning* (pp. 284-298). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Nazir, A., & Wang, Z. (2023). A comprehensive survey of ChatGPT: Advancements, applications, prospects, and challenges. *Meta-radiology*, 100022.
- Niehaus, S, Hartwig, M., Rosen, P., and Wischniewski, S. (2022). An occupational safety and health perspective on human in control and AI. *Frontiers Artificial Intelligence*, 5, Article 868382, 1-15.
- Perez-Cerrolaza, J., Abella, J., Borg, M., Donzella, C., Cerquides, J., Cazorla, F. J., ... & Flores, J. L. (2024). Artificial intelligence for safety-critical systems in industrial and transportation domains: A survey. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 56(7), 1-40.
- Pishgar, M., Issa, S. F., Sietsema, M., Pratap, P., & Darabi, H. (2021). REDECA: a novel framework to review artificial intelligence and its applications in occupational safety and health. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(13), 6705.
- Pluralsight. (2024). Tech forecast: The top tech trends, tools, and skills to know in 2024. Accessed on September 20, 2024 <https://www.pluralsight.com/resource-center/tech-forecast-2024>.
- Resnick, M. (2024). Generative AI and creative learning: Concerns, opportunities, and choices. Accessed on October 27, 2024 <https://mit-genai.pubpub.org/pub/gj6eod3e/release/2>.
- Russel, S. & Novig, P. (2010). *Artificial intelligence - a moderate approach*. New Jersey: Pearson Education.
- Sandu, N., & Gide, E. (2019, September). Adoption of AI-Chatbots to enhance student learning experience in higher education in India. In *2019 18th International Conference on Information Technology Based Higher Education and Training (ITHET)* (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- Schorr, H., & Rappaport, A. (Eds.). (1989). *Innovative applications of artificial intelligence*. AAAI Press.
- SGS. (2024). Safety ISO 26262. Accessed on 10-27-2024. <https://try.sgs.com/en-us/holistic-automotive-management-system/>.
- Shah, I. A., & Mishra, S. (2024). Artificial intelligence in advancing occupational health and safety: an encapsulation of developments. *Journal of Occupational Health*, 66(1), uiad017.
- Shen, T., Jin, R., Huang, Y., Liu, C., Dong, W., Guo, Z., ... & Xiong, D. (2023). Large language model alignment: A survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2309.15025*.
- Snowflake. (2024). Data + AI predictions 2024. Accessed on September 20, 2024. <https://www.snowflake.com/webinars/thought-leadership/2024-financial-services-data-ai-predictions/>.
- Supiano, B. (2023). Will chatGPT change how professors assess lessons? *Big Bot Bot on Campus, The Chronicle of Higher Education*. Accessed October 29, 2024 <https://www.chronicle.com/article/will-chatgpt-change-how-professors-assess-learning>.
- Walsh, M., Ross, D., Worrell, C. and Gomez, A. (2023). *Harnessing the power of large language models for economic and social good: foundations*. Carnegie Mellon University. Access on August 24th, 2024. <https://insights.sei.cmu.edu/blog/harnessing-the-power-of-large-language-models-for-economic-and-social-good-foundations/>. doi.org/10.58012/gthz-ag46.

MAIN AUTHOR

Dr. David GILKEY is a Professor at Montana Technological University in Butte, MT, USA. Dr. Gilkey earned his Doctor of Chiropractic degree from Southern California Health Sciences University and Ph.D. from Colorado State University with a focus on occupational and environmental health, safety, industrial hygiene, and ergonomics. He is a Certified Professional Ergonomist (CPE), Safety Professional (CSP), and Registered Environmental Health Specialist (REHS/RS). He recently became a Certified XL Tribometrist (CXLT) and NSFI Walkway Auditor Certificate Holder (WACH). Dr. Gilkey has authored and/or coauthored 55 articles in peer-reviewed scientific journals, more than 60 articles in trade journals, and provided four book chapter contributions in the areas of ergonomics, occupational safety, and environmental health. His research has recently included investigating the slip resistance of walkway surfaces. He has been conducting research in construction safety climate for many years. He has also worked in mining safety climate research with an emphasis on assisting companies in developing interventions to improve safety in their operations. He also methods to enhance safe work practices in agriculture where recreational off-road vehicles (ATV and UTV) are used in farm and ranch operations. developing strategies to identify, assess, and manage financial and operational risks.

